

Work-School Environment in Relation to Teachers' Productivity in Tugbok District, Davao City

Jenny Rose B. De Asis

Abstract. The study navigated the relationship between the work-school environment and teachers' productivity in Tugbok District, Davao City. A non-experimental quantitative research design was employed, and data were collected from 250 elementary school teachers through stratified sampling. Modified survey questionnaires assessed the work-school environment and teacher's productivity. The findings revealed an extensive work-school climate in Tugbok District, Davao City, regarding the physical condition and good employee management. Likewise, the extent of the teachers' productivity in Tugbok District, Davao City. In terms of Compensation, work motivation, and self-discipline was extensive. There was a relationship between the work-school environment and teachers' productivity. All the domains in the work-school environment significantly influenced Teachers' Productivity. This provides empirical evidence that the indicators enumerated under Teachers' Productivity could account for and explain the variability of the work-school environment. These findings support the existing literature highlighting the importance of a good and functional workplace in understanding the perspectives of teachers' working conditions. Thus, the teacher will have a positive self-image, value his job, and give it his all. The study provides valuable insights for the Department of Education, Administrators, Teachers, and future researchers to understand better the importance of those above in fostering a much better learning community for students and everyone in it.

KEY WORDS

1. educational management 2. work-school environment 3. teachers' productivity

Date Received: May 25, 2024 — Date Reviewed: June 01, 2024 — Date Published: July 1, 2024

1. Introduction

The physical environment in the workplace is essential for employee performance, satisfaction, social relationships, and health. The physical work environment is all physical conditions found around the workplace that can directly or indirectly affect employees. A productive work environment was conducive to focus and concentration. It was a space where employees felt comfortable and supported and where they had the resources they needed to do their best work. A conducive working environment was a catalyst for employee productivity. When employees feel comfortable and valued, they are naturally more motivated to excel in their roles. They were more likely to invest their time and energy in their tasks, which led to higher productivity and innovative thinking. In contrast, The Teacher's work productivity was critical and vital for attaining an excellent education. In the global aspect of this study, based on his

study findings, Sultana Mahbuba (2013) found that individuals' increased job productivity significantly determines an organization's success or failure. Gilmore Sutikno (2011) states that work productivity is the influence or ability of an individual to produce more inspired, procreative output that produces aids and benefits. It means that the work productivity of educators and educational personnel must also be improved to increase productivity. Teachers, as professional and functional staff, are accountable for carrying out the school's primary duties and functions, namely instigating education and learning services for students, and they have the most substantial influence on school productivity. The tasks in the teacher's primary tasks and functions can be used to determine the productivity of the teacher's job. According to Yuliandri and Kristiawan (2017), teacher effectiveness may also raise the caliber of instruction and learning. The primary duties and responsibilities of this sort of teacher include a) organizing the teaching and learning activities, b) carrying those out, c) evaluating the teaching and learning results, d) supervising and instructing the students, and e) doing other duties. According to recent studies, teacher productivity is the most essential component of a school's influence on student learning, and there is significant variety in teacher productivity within and among schools (Rockoff (2004). However, more information about what makes specific instructors more productive in boosting student accomplishment than others is needed. The first few years of teaching experience increase productivity, but nothing else regarding observed teacher traits appears to matter consistently. As a result, while teachers significantly influence student success, the variance in teacher productivity must be accounted for mainly by routinely assessed teacher attributes. One possible explanation for current research's inability to uncover the causes of teacher productivity is that researchers need to evaluate the factors that genuinely affect productivity. Recent labor economics research, for example, reveals that personality qualities like conscientiousness play a crucial role in predicting worker productivity (Borghans et al., 2008). However, the proportional predictive value of cognitive and non-cognitive characteristics is difficult to examine due to the difficulties in acquiring measurements of cognitive and non-cognitive abilities and labor productivity. Unraveling the characteristics linked to teacher productivity might provide significant insights into the best practices for hiring and developing teachers. If personality traits that are measurable beforehand impact teacher productivity, they might be used to screen applications and identify the most desirable individuals throughout the recruiting process. Suppose essential teacher attributes, such as subject matter knowledge, are adaptable. In that case, comprehending which teacher characteristics influence student learning most might inform the design of pre-service and in-service teacher training programs. The environment is well-defined as the whole lot that surrounds us and influences our ability to exist on the planet, including the water covering most of the earth's surface and the plants and animals surrounding us. The bodily environment includes lighting, temperature, humidity, circulation, noise, mechanical adjustments, disagreeable odors, color arrangement, decorations, music, and safety (Sedarmayanti, 2011; Waheed Kaur, 2016). The work environment, mainly where learning is cultivated and fonder, is the conditions or surroundings in which a student acquires to attain the objective of education. According to Omotere (2013), healthy student-teacher interactions, instructors' qualifications, libraries, labs, appropriate circulation scheduling, solid instructional design, accessibility to teaching resources, and managerial forecasting are all aspects of the work environment that are crucial to the teacher-learning process. It is acknowledged that a well-run school

may create predictable educational outcomes for its learners, including political freedom, active teaching, financial freedom, learning processes, educational actions, and social freedom. According to published research, most schools needed more classroom space, furniture, light, water, and restrooms. (Ain, Kaur Waheed, 2016; Saeed Wain, 2011; Sanni, 2013). It is also stated in the study of Wechsler et al. (2000) that "environment" in the academic context refers to "outside conditions that have a significant impact on school organization and student achievements." Additionally, skilled instructors, book and library resources, laboratory workspace, and equipment are affected. The environment also comprises the school's furniture and competent management personnel, and the relationship between these elements significantly impacts the organization. The school's environment functions as an invisible thread that ties all the parts together for a specific reason, thus essential to maintaining the school's excellent health. According to Malone and Tranter (2003), the physical environment of a school is known as the school grounds and buildings, and it impacts the health and safety of both instructors and children. MicZais (2011) stated that a school environment is a combination of circumstances that improves the safety and health of kids and instructors. Children are also drawn to schools because they have fences, water and bathroom facilities, and trained and qualified teachers. Afework and Asfaw (2014) looked at available school facilities and how they affect the quality of education. Kuncoro and Dardiri (2017) noted that instructors' poor performance in giving lessons was always attributed to the working environment, including workplace, physical, and psychological conditions. Teaching and learning were negatively affected by a lack of support for teachers in their work environment. Teachers might be more productive if they had a safe and comfortable workplace. Mangkunegara (2018) said that teachers at ed-

ucational institutions could achieve their full potential with the proper working conditions. According to Suwatno and Priansa (2018), the elements that impact the working environment typically include the workplace's physical and psychological aspects. According to Hernando et al. (2018), the work environment affects the teacher's personality and other coworkers, affecting the teacher's performance. Olufemii and Olayinka (2017) and Limon (2016) say that school buildings directly affect how well students and teachers do their jobs. As Alam et al. (2022) discovered, more skilled and experienced instructors were also responsible for their pupils' physical and psychological requirements. Primary schools designated for early childhood education have overcrowded classrooms and need more appropriate teaching and learning resources. Similarly, Moosvi (2022) studied that parents want to avoid sending their kids to school because they have seen how bad the learning environment is (school buildings, boundary walls, drinking water, toilets, and how few school supplies there are. This is made worse by the fact that many public school teachers need more basic training and struggle to teach their students in a way that is efficient, effective, and engaging. Therefore, the school environment significantly impacts the performance of instructors and students at all educational levels. In this regard, the following objectives and research questions were developed. Most public school teachers in the Davao Region clamor regarding the voluminous workload added to their daily routine. This, in turn, makes them unmotivated to fulfill their tasks, making their teaching life meaningless. Teachers with low productivity have a detrimental influence on their colleagues, undermine the credibility of other school personnel, and degrade the school's performance and outcomes. The most critical component of the teaching-learning process is the instructor. The teacher determines the classroom's atmosphere and lighting. He serves as

the figure of authority who guides conduct. He acts as a benchmark and is purposefully emulated. Thus, excellent and productive teachers are essential for the effective functioning of the education system and for improving the quality of learning. Also, given the complex and te-

dious work of handling these kinds of learners, this study seeks to find out how these teachers cope, given that there are many contributing factors, such as environmental factors, which will thus be the focal point of this research. That is why this study was conducted.

2. Methodology

This section contains the research design, research respondents, research instrument, data gathering procedure, and data analysis.

2.1. Research Design—This study applied quantitative research to determine the influence of the work-school environment on teachers' productivity in Tugbok District, Davao City, in terms of compensation, work motivation, and discipline. Quantitative research was presented in numerical form and analyzed using statistics, and the proponents tended to use mathematical models as the methodology of data analysis; it includes collecting data so that the information can be quantified and subjected to statistical treatment to support or refute alternate knowledge claims (Williams, 2017). This study comprises one independent and one dependent variable with corresponding indicators that would affect the abovementioned variable. Hence, the researchers use a test instrument as the main gathering tool to assess the environment's influence on teachers' productivity. The researchers consider this design to help them gather the needed data and propose concrete guidelines regarding teachers' productivity analysis, if any.

2.2. Research Respondents—The study's respondents were elementary school teachers in Tugbok District, Davao City. In this study, the 250 respondents were selected through a stratified random sampling technique. Stratified random sampling was a method of sampling that involved the division of a population into smaller sub-groups known as strata. According to Shi (2015), in stratified random sampling, or stratification, the strata are formed based on

members' shared attributes or characteristics, such as income or educational attainment. Stratified random sampling was appropriate in this study because there is heterogeneity in a population that could be classified with ancillary information. In this study, certain inclusion criteria were implemented to determine the respondents. The primary consideration of this study was to select respondents who could provide information to achieve the purpose of this study. Hence, only those permanent-regular teachers in Tugbok District, Davao City, those who were not subjected to any administrative or criminal cases, and those who voluntarily signed the ICF were given the survey questionnaires. Moreover, the study was delimited only to the nature of the problem based on the research questions, and thus, it did not consider the teachers' performance ratings.

2.3. Research Instrument—This study uses the adopted-modified questionnaire. This means that the questionnaire was adopted from different sources, such as the Internet, and modified to contextualize the professional setting and simplify the question items for the respondents' understanding. The following scale was used to determine the level of influence of the work-school environment on teachers' productivity. Experts validated the content of the questions used in this study to safeguard the rationality and dependability of the study and ensure that the questionnaire's content was appropriate for the study.

Range, Descriptive Equivalent, and Descriptive Interpretation of Work-School Environment

Range	Descriptive Equivalent	Descriptive Interpretation
4.20 – 5.00	Very Extensive	This means that the work-school environment is very much observed.
3.40 – 4.19	Extensive	This means that the work-school environment is much observed.
2.60 – 3.39	Moderately Extensive	This means that the work-school environment is fairly observed.
1.80 – 2.59	Less Extensive	This means that the work-school environment is less observed.
1.00 – 1.79	Not Extensive	This means that the work-school environment is not observed.

Range, Descriptive Equivalent, and Descriptive Interpretation of Work-School Environment Among Teachers’ Productivity

Range	Descriptive Equivalent	Descriptive Interpretation
4.20 – 5.00	Very Extensive	This means that the work-school environment among teachers’ productivity is very much observed.
3.40 – 4.19	Extensive	This means that the work-school environment among teachers’ productivity is much observed.
2.60 – 3.39	Moderately Extensive	This means that the work-school environment among teachers’ productivity is fairly observed.
1.80 – 2.59	Less Extensive	This means that the work-school environment among teachers’ productivity is less observed.
1.00 – 1.79	Not Extensive	This means that the work-school environment among teachers’ productivity is not observed.

2.4. *Data Gathering Procedure*—After the validation of the research questionnaire, the researcher would undergo specific steps in conducting the study: Permission to Conduct the Study. The researcher obtained permission to conduct the study by securing an endorsement from the Dean of the Graduate School at Rizal

Memorial Colleges, Inc., Davao City. The endorsement letter was attached to the permission letters addressed to the school principals of the selected public elementary schools in Tugbok District, Davao City. The researcher contacted the identified respondents in Tugbok District, Davao City, and explained the research study,

seeking their consent to participate. A link to the survey and consent form was sent to the principals to maintain anonymity, who then forwarded it to the respondents. A comprehensive explanation of the voluntary nature of the study accompanied the link, and paper copies were provided upon request. The email communication assured the participants that their school principals had granted prior approval. Distribution and Retrieval of the Questionnaire. Following the approval to conduct the study, the researcher distributed the questionnaires to the respondents. During this process, the researcher briefly discussed the benefits of the survey and clarified the identified respondents. The

questionnaire administration strictly adhered to health protocols, including the use of face masks and shields and adherence to social distancing guidelines. Sufficient time was given to the respondents to complete the questionnaires. After collecting the data, it was subjected to quantitative analysis. Collation and Statistical Treatment of Data. Once the questionnaires were retrieved, the researcher tallied each respondent's scores to organize the data according to the indicators. Subsequently, the scores underwent descriptive and inferential analysis using the Statistical Package for the Social Sciences (SPSS) software.

2.5. *Data Analysis*—The researcher utilized the following statistical tools to process the gathered data: Mean. This statistical tool was used in this study to compute the influence of the work-school environment on teachers' productivity in Tugbok District, Davao City. Pearson-r. This study used this statistical tool

to determine the relationship between the work-school environment and teachers' productivity in Tugbok District, Davao City. Multiple Regression Analysis. This statistical tool was used in this study to determine the influence of the work-school environment on teachers' productivity in Tugbok District, Davao City.

3. Results and Discussion

This chapter discusses the problems in this study. They are thoroughly discussed, analyzed, and interpreted. The data gathered, and the results of this quantitative study were also presented. Various tables illustrate the influence of the work-school environment on physical condition and good employee management, as well as the assessment of teachers' productivity concerning compensation, work motivation, and discipline.

The Summary of the Extent of Work School Environment

Table 1 presents the mean scores for the pointers, a summary of the extent of the work-school environment in Tugbok District, Davao City. The overall mean score is 4.03, indicating an extensive rating provided by the respondents in all indicators. The overall result signifies that the respondents' responses to the work-school environment were mainly positive, particularly regarding the physical condition and good employee management. Good employee manage-

ment, with the highest mean of 4.06, showed a positive correlation as an indicator of the work-school environment concerning teachers' productivity in Tugbok District, Davao City. This meant that it was also a factor for an efficient working environment that was good and well taken care of by management for employees. Physical condition or environment emerged as the primary work-school environment indicator, showcasing a positive result regarding teachers' productivity with the highest mean. Most respondents believed that the teaching staff played

a crucial role in supporting the teaching and learning processes, ensuring learners received appropriate accommodations. Consequently, school facilities served as the school curriculum’s spatial interpretation and physical expression. This suggested that the work-school environment positively impacted elementary school

teachers in Tugbok District, Davao City. Finally, the cited overall mean score represents the result collected from the following computed mean scores, ranked from highest to lowest: 3.99. This indicates an extensive rating for physical condition, signifying the more significant factors for the student’s learning interest.

Table 1. The Summary of the Work-School Environment in Tugbok District, Davao City

Indicator	Mean	Descriptive Equivalent
1. Physical condition	3.99	Extensive
2. Good employee management	4.06	Extensive
Overall Mean	4.03	Extensive

The above results was parallel to the study presented by Carter Jr. (2021). The literature presents a myriad of fundamental issues that contribute to a toxic, oppressive, and ineffective workplace environment, resulting in teachers of color leaving schools and, ultimately, the workforce. In response to their workplace conditions, the literature offers suggestions for improving the work environment for teachers of color through professional development, affinity groups, and representation. This list is incomplete; however, we understand that this must be addressed on a case-by-case basis as, for some, it could be a simple building or district policy change, while for others, more significant systemic state and departmental policy may need to be addressed. This finding was supported by Bourke Dillon (2018), who asserted that their research on the workplace environment for teachers of color is still growing and further honing in on more specific and nuanced ways of understanding how they navigate school spaces. This brief is meant to assist schools and educational spaces begin to alter their workplace environments to become more inclusive, safe,

and inviting for teachers of color in efforts not simply to recruit and retain them but to embed and normalize their contributions value systematically and place in schools. Teachers of color have also indicated that seeing representation in the classroom in other roles is also beneficial. Embedding paraprofessionals in the community allows students to access their cultural capital and integrate community knowledge into the learning process. Making space for elders and other community members in schools helps create inclusive spaces that feel inviting and safe for the SOC and the teachers and leaders of color as schools are diversified and are no longer viewed as “white spaces.” The work-school environment, in terms of teachers’ productivity in Tugbok District, Davao City, was high. It entailed that most of the respondents were much more productive when the surrounding school had enough facilities for conducive learning. Most respondents believed that it was the vital role of the teaching staff to support the teaching and learning that took place there, and learners were given the appropriate accommodations. Therefore, school facilities were the

space interpretation and physical expression of the school curriculum. This meant that the work-school environment positively impacted elementary school teachers in Tugbok District, Davao City. Moreover, this indicated that the respondents' response to the work-school environment was highly commendable across all indicators, namely physical condition and good employee management. This result aligns with the theory of Earthman, G. (2002), which posits that school building design features and components have a measurable influence on student learning. Overcrowded school buildings and classrooms have been shown to influence student performance, especially for minority students negatively. Previous studies have employed specific building features or components, such as air conditioning, lighting, or windows, as variables to compare student achievement. Among work-school environment indicators, physical condition had the highest mean described as high. It indicated that most elementary school teachers in Tugbok District, Davao City, tended to focus more on specific aspects such as noise when considering environmental effects on education and learning, often failing to synthesize understandings (for instance, noise and temperature research implications frequently disagree). There is clear evidence that extremes of envi-

ronmental elements have adverse effects on students and teachers and that improving these elements has significant benefits, which confirms Higgins et al. (2005). Teachers' working environment is essential to them and, eventually, to their pupils. Regardless of the student demographics at the school, teachers are happier and more willing to work in environments that are conducive for an extended period.

The Summary of The Extent of the Teachers' Productivity

Presented in Table 2 is the summary of the extent of the teachers' productivity in Tugbok District, Davao City. The overall mean rating of the data in this table is (3.86). The three indicators are presented with the corresponding mean: Compensation (3.99), work motivation (4.03), and self-discipline (3.55). These indicators got a mean rating (3.98) with the descriptive equivalent of Extensive., it indicated that teachers were motivated by compensation because "less pay compared to work done is one of those extrinsic factors that are responsible for job dissatisfaction." Job satisfaction was the most crucial factor in every organization since only those organizations flourished if their employees were satisfied with their work environment and compensation system.

Table 2. Summary of Teachers' Productivity

Indicators	Mean (\bar{x})
Compensation	3.99
Work Motivation	4.03
Self-Discipline	3.55
Overall mean	3.86

The result reveals that the teachers were motivated to perform and achieve to deliver their instructional role in the classroom and help the students increase their social engagement. To accomplish and prepare practical lessons, grade

student work and offer feedback, manage classroom materials, productively navigate the curriculum, and collaborate with other staff. This was supported by Van Wart (2008), who continues that recognition is a motivational strategy

that is very important; it is an intangible incentive that shows gratitude and offers praise. However, it has yet to be utilized by most managers in the organization. He further said that recognition has an optimistic meaning, and it acknowledges good behavior or actions. The finding is affirmed by Egan (2012), who said students' relationships with supportive teachers are expected to promote a sense of connectedness in the classroom, which should result in less problematic behavior and enhanced prosocial behavior. Student reports of teacher affiliation have been positively linked to engagement in the learning process and to time on task (Hamre Pianta, 2001). Student reports of teacher affiliation also have been linked to fewer problems (Crosnoe, Johnson, Elder, 2004) and risk-taking behaviors, resulting in greater school attendance and academic achievement (Centers for Disease Control and Prevention, 2009). International Task Force on Teachers for Education 2030 (2022) reported that the effects of this are serious pay disparity, and it is quickly developing into a crisis. Low salaries make it harder to attract new teachers and retain those already in the profession. When college graduates see their peers offered better salaries and a better lifestyle in other professions, it can become difficult to convince them to pursue teaching. It has been shown that increasing starting salaries would make teaching more appealing, increasing competition for jobs and raising the standard of applicants. As a consequence the social status of teaching as a profession would rise, boosting teacher motivation. They added that as for retention, it's often the best teachers – those who work the hardest and go above and beyond for their students – who become disillusioned when their efforts go unrecognized. Eventually, many are driven to seek a better lifestyle in another line of work. The result is related to the theory of Sultana Mahbuba (2013), which suggest that an individual's job productivity increase significantly determines an orga-

nization's success or failure. Work productivity is the influence or ability of an individual to produce more inspired, proactive output that has aids and benefits. This implies that to increase school productivity, the work productivity of educators and educational personnel also needs to be improved. Teachers, as professional and functional staff, accountable for carrying out the school's primary duties and functions, namely instigating education and learning services for students, have the most substantial influence on grasping school productivity. Among all the teachers' productivity indicators, the compensation had the highest mean, described as high. It indicated that rewards motivate employees because "less pay compared to work done is one of those extrinsic factors that is responsible for job dissatisfaction." Job satisfaction is the most crucial factor in every organization, as only those organizations will flourish if their employees are satisfied with their work environment and compensation system. When people are more comfortable, they are more committed and productive at work because their satisfaction and dissatisfaction depend not only on the job but also on the employee's expectations. In terms of discipline, which had a lower mean, it was described as substandard. This indicated that elementary school teachers in Tugbok District, Davao City, have awareness and willingness to follow all corporate regulations and appropriate social norms. This is anchored on the viewpoint of Kempa Chaterine (2016), which argues that employee performance can suffer due to a lack of job discipline. An employee will complete duties and work effectively and efficiently to boost employee performance and contribute to attaining organizational goals. Finally, work motivation is low, showing the lowest mean as responded by elementary school teachers in Tugbok District, Davao City. This means that the respondents' motivation stimulates people internally to assist them in achieving specific goals or tasks allocated to them. According to

Latief et al. (2018), a highly motivated person will give his all to his work and vice versa. If a person is not motivated to work, there will be no fresh things he can do to help the firm meet its goals. This motivation is critical since each employee is expected to perform hard and joyfully to attain high job productivity. Relationship between Work-School Environment and Teachers' Productivity

Table 3 shows the test of correlations to determine the significance of the relationship be-

tween the work-school environment and teachers' productivity. The results show that the independent variable has a significant relationship with the dependent variable ($p < .05$). In particular, the relationship between work-school environment and teachers' productivity is significant with a p-value ($p = .000$) less than 0.05 and a positive correlation coefficient of 0.415. This implies that when the work-school environment is increased, it would likely lead to a Teachers' Productivity.

Table 3. Relationship between Professional Commitments and Leadership Skills of Teachers

Variables	r-value	Degree of correlation
Relationship between Work-School Environment (x) and Teachers' Productivity (Y)	0.415	Moderate
P-value	Decision	
.000	Reject	

This finding is similar to Smith's (2006) statement that teachers shoulder the responsibility of shaping the nation's future. The future of the nation depends upon the skills and efficiency of the teachers. Teachers are also known as creators. They are the creators of philosophers, leaders, doctors, advocates, and many more. A teacher's job is not at all that easy. Unless a high degree of professional qualities and commitment is inculcated in the teacher's personality, the training program will remain incomplete. Similarly, Edwards, K. (2004) stressed that the teacher's work involves rigorous efforts in the classroom and outside, as well as frequent interaction with parents and community members. For this purpose, teachers need to be well-trained and competent to perform their jobs. If teachers acquire Professional competencies and commitment and if they are enabled and empowered to perform their multiple tasks

in the classroom as well as in the school and community in a genuinely professional manner, then high-quality learning among increasingly more students may result in cognitive, affective and psychomotor areas of human development improving teaching performance through more effective teacher preparation, therefore is an essential ingredient in solving most educational problems.

The Data in the Indicators of Work-School Environment Teachers' Productivity

Table 4 depicts the simple regression coefficient analysis of the significant influence of indicators of the data on indicators of the work-school environment on the Teachers' Productivity. All indicators of the work-school environment, namely physical condition (0.010) and good employee management (0.011), are statistically significant for Teachers' Productivity. This shows that the work-school environment

significantly influences learners’ teachers’ productivity. Meanwhile, the R2 value of 0.887 suggests that the indicators of Work-School Environment can explain 88.7 of the variance in work-school environment outcomes. This provides empirical evidence that the variability of the Work-School Environment can be accounted for and explained by the indicators as enumer-

ated under the Teachers’ Productivity. In addition, the F-value shows all the sums of squares, with regression being the model and Residual being the error. The F-value (235.525) and F-statistic are significant $p < .002$, which indicates that the model significantly predicts Teachers’ Productivity.

Table 4. Regression Coefficient Analysis on Work-School Environment Teachers’ Productivity

Model	B	Beta	Standard Error	p-value	Decisions
H (Intercept)	4.389		0.052	$p < .001$	
H (Intercept)	0.410		0.144	0.006	
Physical condition	0.033	-0.031	0.056	0.010	Reject H0
Good employee management	0.352	0.362	0.064	0.011	Reject H0
R2					
F-value	= 235.525				
p-value	= $p < 0.002$				

*Significant @ $p < 0.05$

The regression coefficient tested the influence of the work-school environment and teachers’ productivity among Tugbok District, Davao City elementary school teachers. Utilizing Linear Regression Analysis, the data showed that the power of the work-school environment concerning teachers’ productivity had a significant influence. Hence, the significance level in the null hypothesis, indicating no vital relationship between the two variables, was rejected. As mentioned in the previous study, the resulting significant relationship conformed with the theory from which this study is anchored. This section has stated several times that the substantial influence of the independent variable on the dependent variable emphasizes the theory’s integrity. This is supported by the study of Nakpodia (2011), who states that a good work environment allows employees to be happy at

their jobs. It is a circumstance in which all the required conditions and facilities to aid instructors in their work will be supplied. This includes things like well-furnished air-conditioned offices with a robust communications and information technology network, instructional tools and materials, a pleasant working environment, and an open organizational climate, among other things. In these settings, the teacher will have a positive self-image, value his job, and give it his all. The findings further provide insight into the implications of teachers’ productivity regarding compensation, work motivation, and discipline. Baharuddin’s study (2021) discovered a strong correlation between a teacher’s work environment and their effectiveness. As a result, teachers’ performance was impacted by their positive, pleasant, secure, and positive work environment.

4. Conclusions and Recommendations

This section of the paper provides the researcher's conclusion and recommendations based on the findings. The conclusions drawn were supported by the existing literature discussed in the earlier chapters, and they address the research problem identified in this study.

4.1. Findings—The study's respondents were elementary school teachers in Tugbok District, Davao City. In this study, the 250 respondents were selected through a stratified random sampling technique. Stratified random sampling was a method of sampling that involved the division of a population into smaller sub-groups known as strata. According to Shi (2015), in stratified random sampling, or stratification, the strata are formed based on members' shared attributes or characteristics, such as income or educational attainment. Stratified random sampling was appropriate in this study because there was heterogeneity in a population that could be classified with ancillary information. Certain inclusion criteria were implemented to determine the respondents. The primary consideration of this study is to select respondents who can provide information to achieve its purpose. Hence, only permanent-regular teachers in Tugbok District, Davao City, those who were not subjected to any administrative or criminal cases, and those who voluntarily signed the ICF were given the survey questionnaires. This was a summary of the extent of the work-school environment in Tugbok District, Davao City. The overall mean score was 4.03, indicating an extensive rating provided by the respondents in all indicators. The overall result signifies that the respondents' responses to the work-school environment were mainly positive, particularly regarding the physical condition and good employee management. While summarizing the extent of the teachers' productivity in Tugbok District, Davao City. The overall mean rating of the data in this table was (3.86). The three indicators are presented with the corresponding mean: Compensation (3.99), work motivation (4.03), and self-discipline (3.55). These indicators got a mean rating (3.98) with the descriptive equivalent of Extensive, which indicated that teachers were motivated by compensation because "less pay compared to work done was one of those extrinsic factors that were responsible for job dissatisfaction." Job satisfaction was crucial in every organization since only those organizations flourished if their employees were. In particular, the relationship between the work-school environment and teachers' productivity is significant, with a p-value ($p = .000$) less than 0.05 and a positive correlation coefficient of 0.415. This implies that when the work-school environment was increased, it would likely lead to a teachers' productivity. The significant influence of indicators of the data on indicators of the work-school environment on the Teachers' Productivity. All indicators of the work-school environment, namely physical condition (0.010) and good employee management (0.011), are statistically significant for Teachers' Productivity. This shows that the work-school environment significantly influences learners' teachers' productivity. Meanwhile, the R^2 value of 0.887 suggests that the indicators of Work-School Environment can explain 88.7 of the variance in work-school environment outcomes. This provides empirical evidence that the variability of the Work-School Environment could be accounted for and presented by the indicators enumerated under the Teachers' Productivity. This follows the study of Perawati, Bukaman Lian, and Tobari (2018), which stated that to achieve maximum productivity, some factors affect the work productivity of the teacher, which are compensation, work motivation, and discipline.

4.2. *Conclusions*—Based on the study’s findings, these conclusions were drawn: The work-school environment in Tugbok District, Davao City, regarding the physical condition and good employee management, was extensive. The extent of the teachers’ productivity in Tugbok District, Davao City. In terms of Compensation, work motivation and self-discipline was extensive. There was a relationship between the work-school environment and teachers’ productivity. All the domains in the work-school environment significantly influenced Teachers’ Productivity. This provides empirical evidence that the variability of the Work-School Environment could be accounted for and explained by the indicators enumerated under Teachers’ Productivity.

4.3. *Recommendations*—The following recommendations were offered in light of the initial findings and conclusions; since there was a relationship between the work-school environment and teachers’ productivity, the following suggestions were made to guarantee the productivity of the primary school teacher. Teaching

aids and equipment may be provided for teachers to promote effective teaching and learning. Teaching may not be made a stepping stone for other professions; instead, it may be made lucrative to command higher socio-economic status as a profession. In addition to salaries and wages, the work environment may be more conducive to academic work. Many teachers would prefer good classrooms and teaching materials to high wages. However, salaries may be attractive enough for teachers to take good care of themselves and their families without working elsewhere to make ends meet. Their salaries and allowances may be paid as they are due. The service conditions of primary school teachers may be the same as those of other government ministries and parastatal workers. Teachers may be encouraged to stay on the job in primary school through motivation. Teacher promotions may be a regular process to motivate them to increase productivity. Retraining primary school teachers may be part and parcel of their working conditions. They may be exposed to unique training programs to increase their earning power and update their working knowledge and skills.

5. References

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